

An Analysis of the Topics within Earth and Planetary Sciences on OpenAlex

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1. Introduction

This report analyzes and evaluates the Knowledge Organization System (KOS) used by OpenAlex, called Topics. Introduced in 2024, OpenAlex Topics replaced Concepts, which were inherited from Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG). Topics are created by clustering the citation network of scholarly works to identify communities, using a large language model (LLM) to label and describe these clusters, and training a machine-learning model to assign Topics to works based on their titles, abstracts, citation relations, and source names (Priem et al., 2022). The Topics KOS contains approximately 4,500 Topics organized into three hierarchical levels: 4 domains, 26 fields, and 252 subfields. Each topic belongs to one subfield, one field, and one domain, and includes descriptive metadata such as display names, keywords, and summaries.

This report focuses on the Earth and Planetary Sciences field and its eight subfields: Paleontology, Earth-Surface Processes, Geochemistry and Petrology, Oceanography, Geophysics, Space and Planetary Science, Atmospheric Science, and Geology. No systematic analysis and evaluation of OpenAlex Topics as a KOS currently exists, making this evaluation both necessary and timely. The report begins with an overview of the existing literature on OpenAlex Topics and how Earth and Planetary Sciences are traditionally classified, then evaluates the Topics KOS using quantitative and qualitative criteria to assess the quality of indexing for the Earth and Planetary Sciences field.

2. Literature Review: OpenAlex as an Academic Research Database

OpenAlex is currently the world's largest open-access database of academic research, integrating key persistent identifiers, including DOIs, ORCIDs, and RORs. Unlike journal-based classification systems, OpenAlex assigns categories at the level of individual articles and designates a single primary category rather than multiple equal ones (Thelwall & Jiang, 2025). Its subject classification hierarchy spans domains, fields, subfields, and Topics. Topics are generated through large-scale clustering of articles, and works are automatically assigned based on metadata signals, including titles, abstracts, journal names, and citation relationships (Thelwall & Jiang, 2025).

Although this report focuses specifically on the Earth and Planetary Sciences field, no prior literature has evaluated OpenAlex Topics in this field or in the broader domain, Physical Sciences. Existing research instead examines OpenAlex as a general-purpose bibliographic database, revealing its strengths and limitations for understanding how well it represents specific scientific domains.

Due to its fully open infrastructure, OpenAlex is more accessible than subscription-based systems and offers notably broader coverage. Culbert et al. (2025)

found that it contains a larger corpus than both Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. Similarly, Céspedes et al. (2025) reported that OpenAlex surpasses these databases in the number of documents and journals indexed. Maddi et al. (2025) found that OpenAlex trends towards better geographical equity than proprietary databases, though it still under-represents Africa and Asia. Its more inclusive indexing policy contributes to broader coverage of open-access journals from around the world. Céspedes et al. (2025) also found that OpenAlex has the potential to make non-English literature more visible and to enable proper assessment of language in the dissemination landscape. It allows for reliable and thorough linguistic analysis (Céspedes et al. 2025). Culbert et al. (2025) found that OpenAlex has high coverage of ORCID and concluded that robust citation analysis requires multidatabase approaches, with OpenAlex serving as a valuable complement to proprietary tools such as Web of Science and Scopus.

Despite this broader coverage, multiple studies highlight significant limitations in metadata accuracy and completeness. Zhang et al. (2024) found that OpenAlex depends on upstream metadata, so errors or omissions in sources such as Crossref are reproduced in OpenAlex. For example, Crossref often lacks institutional information, a gap that persists in OpenAlex. The automated extraction used by OpenAlex struggles with non-standardized formats, group authorship, and inconsistent labelling across publishers (Zhang et al., 2024). The five major causes of missing institutions include unstandardized institution names, group authorship, unstandardized authorship labelling, unstandardized document types, and platform deficiencies. While the missing institution problem is trending downward, social sciences and humanities continue to have more metadata problems than natural sciences, which benefit from greater standardization (Zhang et al., 2024). Zheng et al. (2025) identified similar discrepancies in coverage of China, including incomplete institutional affiliation and inconsistent document-type classification.

These metadata problems directly affect Topic assignment, citation analysis reliability, and the validity of bibliometric assessments across fields, languages, and geographical regions. Alperin et al. (2024) found that many works could not be matched to Scopus due to missing or erroneous metadata and that language detection is less reliable in OpenAlex. They conclude that OpenAlex results must be interpreted with caution, especially in less standard fields, languages, or document types. Thelwall and Jiang (2025) found similar issues in language classification and noted that OpenAlex classifies editorial contributions as standard journal articles, which influences field-normalized citation calculations. They also identified problems with articles lacking any indexed references. However, they determined that OpenAlex is suitable for citation analysis, especially when Scopus is used to support document type classifications. Rodrigues et al. (2025) found many missing citations in Web of Science and Scopus

when using OpenAlex as the baseline. However, Scopus indexes more recent citations than Web of Science and is more rapid than OpenAlex.

Document type classification presents additional challenges. Haupka et al. (2024) found that many records in OpenAlex lack a publication type and that book reviews are classified as articles. Retractions are included in most analyses by default, and compared with other major databases, OpenAlex has the highest coverage of retractions, withdrawals, and retracted articles (Ortega & Delgado-Quirós, 2024). Céspedes et al. (2025) found inconsistencies in the implementation of open access labelling, with full-text access labels sometimes not matching the actual status of documents. Stansfield et al. (2025) found that OpenAlex retrieves many more irrelevant records than other resources for comprehensive literature searching, and that its Boolean search functions are not as sophisticated as those of other databases. Despite these limitations, OpenAlex shows promise for identifying most of the literature in complex yet relatively focused health-related searches (Stansfield et al., 2025). While OpenAlex suffers from imprecise document classifications, recent large-scale comparisons of citation coverage across databases highlight that no single source is comprehensive. OpenAlex must be evaluated as one component within an ecosystem of bibliographic databases (Gusenbauer, 2024).

Beyond general metadata issues, the underlying structure of OpenAlex Topics raises specific concerns. OpenAlex Topics are derived from clustering methods developed initially for the MAG, which grouped papers based on text similarity and citation links (Wang et al., 2020). MAG was discontinued in 2021, so the underlying topic system is no longer updated or reviewed by experts. Studies of MAG show that text-based clustering is less reliable in STEM fields, where terminology varies, and disciplines overlap, making fields like Earth and Planetary Sciences especially vulnerable to fragmented or shifting topics (Boyack & Klavans, 2010; 2017). Research on bibliometric methods also shows that automated clustering performs poorly when citation patterns and topic boundaries do not align well (Waltman & van Eck, 2012).

Haunschild and Bornmann (2024) examined whether OpenAlex could produce meaningful bibliometric global overlay maps of science at the individual, institutional, and national levels. They concluded that Topics are not mature enough. There are multiple Topics with the same content, and many Topics have excessively long names, so only a few can be displayed on a map. They noted weaknesses in the labelling of concepts, including wrong explanatory terms, close vicinity to other concepts, and the inability to merge concepts. The authors found the assignment of concepts to documents problematic, with some concepts erroneously assigned to papers or only partly correct. This aligns with their finding that OpenAlex Topics often lack a clear

subfield structure. Taken together, these issues suggest that OpenAlex Topics may not accurately represent Earth and Planetary Sciences without additional validation.

The existing literature establishes that OpenAlex is the largest open-access bibliographic database and offers broader coverage than Web of Science and Scopus, particularly for non-English publications and underrepresented regions. However, researchers consistently identify significant challenges with metadata accuracy and completeness, including problems with institutional affiliations, document type classification, language detection, and citation indexing. These metadata issues directly affect the reliability of topic assignment, which is critical for this report's focus on Earth and Planetary Sciences, its subfields, and Topics. While OpenAlex shows promise as a complement to proprietary databases, no prior research has systematically evaluated its Topics system specifically for Earth and Planetary Sciences. Given the documented limitations in automated classification and the lack of ongoing expert review since MAG was discontinued, a focused evaluation of how well OpenAlex Topics represents this scientific domain is required.

3. Evaluation

This project aims to critically assess OpenAlex's classification system for the field of Earth and Planetary Sciences. This evaluation is necessary for all KOSs to ensure that a database, particularly one driven by Artificial Intelligence (AI), maintains accuracy, usability, and interoperability. Classification directly impacts scholarly communication, retrieval, and bibliometric analysis, making it crucial to remain efficient, but more importantly, accurate. It is important to evaluate both the structure and the indexing to obtain practical and theoretical insights.

The Earth and Planetary Sciences field spans a broad, interdisciplinary range of subfields. It includes Paleontology, Earth-Surface Processes, Geochemistry and Petrology, Oceanography, Geophysics, Space and Planetary Science, Atmospheric Science, and Geology, all of which are highly relevant to the world we live in today. It also intersects with Environmental Science, Astronomy, Biology, and Climate Studies, meaning that it has direct implications for climate change, natural hazards, and even planetary exploration. Though there were only eight subfields in OpenAlex for Earth and Planetary Sciences, they span a broad and diverse range of topics, making the field rich yet complex to analyze.

Over the course of this research, quantitative methods involving Excel tools to analyze granularity, distribution, and relations to the fields and subfields were used. Out of this emerged metrics for a number of concepts, including the depth of hierarchies and the frequency of relations. Conversely, a variety of qualitative methods were employed, including domain expertise and a literature review to assess logical representation, completeness, and consistency. Following this was a comparative analysis with other

classification systems, such as the Scopus All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) codes, to see how OpenAlex compares. Throughout the analysis, breadth (an overview of all subfields) is combined with depth (examples of selected Topics) to provide a balanced perspective and address time limitations and expertise constraints.

The scope of this research encompasses the entire field of Earth and Planetary Science, including its subfields and topics. As there were not many subfields, it was possible to analyze each subfield and 200 randomly selected publications to assess whether they had been classified correctly, thereby allowing a relatively thorough analysis of OpenAlex's classification capabilities and accuracy. This research focuses primarily on OpenAlex and neglects to do a comprehensive comparison with other KOSs. The center of this research will focus on the structure and indexing of OpenAlex rather than citation metrics or bibliometric performance.

The first section will primarily focus on a general analysis of the classification system, going over structure, completeness, consistency, and interoperability. Following that will be an investigation into the indexing, with a focus on accuracy, granularity, and comparative analysis. Lastly, will come the synthesis and reflection to ensure a comprehensive, structured, and academically rigorous evaluation of OpenAlex in the field of Earth and Planetary Science.

3.1 Classification System Evaluation

To begin, it is essential to examine the structural foundations of how OpenAlex organizes Earth and Planetary Science, since the arrangement of concepts, hierarchies, and semantic relations determines both the clarity and usability of the system. The hierarchy is only three levels deep, with the field (Earth and Planetary Science) being the broadest, followed by subfields, which are larger categories that begin to narrow the field, and lastly topics, which are the smallest and most specific categories.

Figure 1. A taxonomic chart showing the field of Earth and Planetary Science, the eight subfields contained in the field, and the varying number of topics within each subfield

Earth and Planetary Science had only eight subfields, with 57 topics within them. That makes it a relatively small hierarchy despite the massive breadth of Earth and Planetary Science. While most subfields had an average of seven topics, Atmospheric Science had 13, while Space and Planetary Science had only one.

Figure 2. A pie chart showing the distribution of topics per subfield in the field of Earth and Planetary Science

This demonstrates an imbalance in the way OpenAlex structured this field and raises questions about whether it is the optimal way to categorize the field. Neither the subfield with 13 topics nor the subfield with one is optimal from a granular perspective. Coarse granularity aids simplicity and ease of understanding, but risks oversimplification, which is not ideal for a classification system. Conversely, fine granularity provides the precision that coarse granularity lacks, but risks fragmentation. These findings indicate a clear imbalance across subfields, identifying overrepresented and underrepresented areas. A variety of different reasons could spark this imbalance. This could be an indicator of historical emphasis on certain topics and a knowledge gap for others. Technology has developed in ways that assist new research and breakthroughs for certain subfields, while others remain stagnant. Another possibility is that some subfields are more popular than others and have accumulated more publications and public interest, requiring a larger and more diverse subfield and topics to be created. The final potential answer to this question is that OpenAlex has simply made errors in the classification of publications, therefore skewing the numbers in favour of one subfield over others.

When it comes to the semantic relationships between the hierarchical levels, they, for the most part, made logical sense. Seismic Waves and Analysis was located under Geophysics, and Marine and Coastal Ecosystems were located under Oceanography. Some topics, while they generally fit the related subfield, were perhaps

not the best or most accurate fit. An example of this would be the topic Marine Biology and Ecology Research under the subfield Oceanography. While this topic technically fits Oceanography, when going back to the main field of Earth and Planetary Sciences, or even further back to the domain of Physical Sciences, Biology does not fit within any of these. So, while it fits the subfield, it does not fall within the broader context of the Physical Sciences.

These issues demonstrate a clear interoperability gap in OpenAlex when it comes to reading topics not only within subfields but also in the context of the broader field and domain. This can create either cross-disciplinary overlaps between domains, such as Physical Sciences and Life Sciences, or gaps in Life Sciences, as some publications that should be attributed to those fields, subfields, and topics are being classified under another domain altogether. Semantic relationships are crucial for correctly classifying publications and are one major area where AI has fallen short. It was unable to handle the linguistic nuance that humans subconsciously translate, and therefore misclassified a variety of publications into the wrong domain, fields, subfields, or topics, and sometimes all four. Having outlined the structural characteristics, the next step is to consider whether the classification adequately covers the breadth of knowledge in Earth and Planetary Sciences, which brings us to the issue of completeness.

Completeness addresses whether OpenAlex's taxonomy fully represents the domain of Earth and Planetary Sciences, including both established subfields and emerging areas of inquiry. Of the 200 articles randomly sampled under Earth and Planetary Sciences on OpenAlex, only 73 were in Scopus. Of those 73, only 46 were under Earth and Planetary Sciences in Scopus. The remaining 27 were divided up between other categories, from engineering to the computer sciences. Some were under multiple fields and ended up being classified as multidisciplinary. Lastly, there was one that was categorized under the arts and humanities field. In OpenAlex, many of the topics were similar or had overlap, while others were too broad. This implies that OpenAlex had difficulties finding a middle ground where the taxonomies were not too specific but also were open enough that a variety of publications could fit within them. Unlike Scopus, which may classify a work under multiple fields, OpenAlex always assigns a single field, leading to issues with works that are interdisciplinary. There was also a gap in subfields and topics for emerging fields of study. Things like Climate Modelling were located under topics for imaging and AI in the Geology subfield. These gaps affect interdisciplinary work and limit the ability to track cutting-edge research.

While completeness is crucial, it is equally important to ensure that the relationships among concepts are logically consistent, which leads to an evaluation of consistency. Consistency evaluates whether OpenAlex maintains coherent semantic relations across its hierarchies, avoiding skipped levels, circular definitions, or ambiguous overlaps between related concepts. The hierarchy did remain fairly

consistent, and for the most part, the topics made logical sense under their subfield. For example, the topic Atmospheric Chemistry and Aerosols was the child of Atmospheric Science, which fell under Earth and Planetary Sciences. There was, however, a circular reference: Space and Planetary Science had only one child, the topic Archaeological Research and Protection. This demonstrates an error in how the subfields and topics are created and is a structural anomaly. There was also inconsistent formatting and terminology within the topics. Under Geophysics, the topic Earthquake and tectonic studies was written in all lowercase, while Seismic Waves and Analysis was capitalized. This indicates minor discrepancies in how OpenAlex indexes items and a general lack of consistency, even within standard capitalization formats.

Together, these structural evaluations provide a foundation for understanding how the field of Earth and Planetary Sciences is represented in OpenAlex. While this section has provided insight into the organization, completeness, and consistency of OpenAlex's taxonomy for Earth and Planetary Sciences, classification alone does not guarantee effective knowledge retrieval. The next section, therefore, extends the evaluation by examining the indexing process, assessing whether the assigned topics faithfully represent the content of scholarly articles and whether hierarchical structures are respected in practice.

3.2 Indexing Evaluation

Evaluating indexing requires a clear methodological framework, beginning with the selection of representative articles and the comparison of OpenAlex's automated topic assignments with human classifications. After assessing each subfield, a random sample of 200 articles across various topics was selected and analyzed to ensure accurate indexing. OpenAlex's indexing was compared to the human indexing to determine whether it fit at all and, if so, whether it was the best overall fit. This was done to properly ensure the reliability and validity of the evaluation. With the methodology established, we can now assess how accurately OpenAlex's indexing reflects the content of scholarly outputs. Accuracy of representation considers whether the topics assigned by OpenAlex genuinely capture the subject matter of Earth and Planetary Sciences publications, highlighting both strengths and weaknesses in the indexing process.

The indexing generally had good representation across the subfields, with the notable exception of one subfield with one topic. Aside from that, there was decent breadth in the diversity of subfields. The topics were where the most inconsistencies were found, with some being too broad and others being overly specific. Two topics under Geology had identical descriptions, with the only difference being the location where the research took place. The problem is that if there was a publication that perfectly matched that description but was not in one of those two locations, it had to go into another topic, which was less accurate and specific. Several times, OpenAlex

indexed publications that were not in that location to a topic that was clearly described as being from a specific region. Aside from these semantic errors, in fields that were longstanding and well-established, indexing accuracy was higher overall. Conversely, in newer or interdisciplinary fields, OpenAlex struggled to accurately assign the best possible classification. A prime example of this is how climate change has been found across multiple domains and fields. Since climate change is a broad topic, publications about it can fall into a variety of places, and it can be difficult to consolidate all publications about climate change in one location. Beyond accuracy, it is also necessary to examine how indexing interacts with hierarchical structures, particularly whether articles are classified at the appropriate level of granularity.

A critical dimension of evaluating OpenAlex's indexing in Earth and Planetary Sciences is how well it respects hierarchical structures, particularly in terms of granularity and parent-child topic assignments. In practice, granularity often determines whether articles are indexed broadly under umbrella categories such as Geology or more narrowly under specialized topics like Volcanology or Paleoclimatology. While a broad assignment can ensure that articles are captured in general searches, it risks obscuring the distinctive contributions of subfields and may lead to overgeneralization. Conversely, overly narrow assignments can fragment the literature, making it difficult for users to locate relevant work unless they already know the precise terminology. Ideally, an article on volcanic gas emissions should be indexed under both Volcanology and its parent Geology, thereby supporting retrieval at multiple levels of specificity. However, OpenAlex appeared to assign only the child topic, which limits discoverability for users searching at broader levels. Such practices have direct implications for recall and precision. Broader indexing aids recall but reduces precision, while narrower indexing enhances precision but risks excluding interdisciplinary or contextually relevant work. These hierarchical considerations highlight the importance of calibrating indexing practices to balance granularity, ensure parent-child consistency, and optimize discoverability across diverse user needs, from domain specialists to interdisciplinary researchers. To deepen this evaluation, it is useful to compare OpenAlex's indexing practices to those of other databases, which provides a broader perspective on its relative strengths and limitations.

A comparative evaluation situates OpenAlex alongside other classification systems such as Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus, allowing us to identify differences in topic assignment and indexing quality, and reveals both strengths and limitations in its approach to Earth and Planetary Sciences. Earth and Planetary Sciences is not included in the Web of Science core collection subject categories (Clarivate, 2025). The general categories are Arts & Humanities, Science & Technology, and Social Sciences. However, WoS does include similar subject areas to OpenAlex's subfields under Science & Technology, such as Geology, Meteorology & Atmospheric Sciences, Oceanography, Geochemistry & Geophysics, Paleontology, and Astronomy &

Astrophysics. Scopus uses All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) codes to classify the items in its database (Clarivate, n.d.). There is an ASJC code for Earth and Planetary Sciences (19, the same field number as in OpenAlex). Scopus has the following subcodes for Earth and Planetary Science: Earth and Planetary Sciences (miscellaneous), Atmospheric Science, Computers in Earth Sciences, Earth-Surface Processes, Economic Geology, Geochemistry and Petrology, Geology, Geophysics, Geotechnical Engineering and Engineering Geology, Oceanography, Paleontology, Space and Planetary Science and Stratigraphy (Elsevier, n.d.). Thirteen compared to OpenAlex's eight, though all eight align with the Scopus subcodes.

Scopus tends to emphasize broad disciplinary categories, grouping Earth Sciences under large umbrellas that facilitate general retrieval but often overlook finer distinctions. OpenAlex distinguishes itself through its open access model and machine-readable topic structures, which make it highly adaptable for large-scale bibliometric analysis. However, its indexing sometimes lacks the granularity or consistency observed in proprietary systems, particularly in interdisciplinary domains where boundaries are fluid. These differences have significant implications. At the same time, OpenAlex's accessibility and API functionality provide unique advantages for researchers seeking scalable, customizable analyses. The comparative evaluation underscores that while OpenAlex offers valuable openness and adaptability, users must remain aware of its limitations and, where necessary, supplement it with other databases to ensure comprehensive coverage.

To determine whether OpenAlex papers were indexed under the correct topic, we started with a sample of 13 papers to assess whether all three evaluators agreed on whether the topic fit the paper and, when it did, whether it was the best fit for the assigned paper. Our test found that we agreed on the topic fit 97.44% of the time and that we agreed completely (on both the fit and whether the topic was the best fit) 87.18% of the time. Since agreement was high, we determined that going forward, the remaining papers, which were to be assessed for topic fit, could be safely divided between the three authors.

When evaluating topic fit to papers, we used a random sample of 200 papers from the field of Earth and Planetary Sciences¹. The selected number of papers from each topic was weighted to ensure that a truly random representation of the field was provided based on the total number of papers per topic under OpenAlex.

When determining the fit, we found that 144 (72%) of the papers were assigned a topic that was a good fit. 123 of the 144 papers that had a good fit were also assigned a topic that was the best fit for that paper. This shows that while OpenAlex's paper indexing is not perfect, it is quite helpful and assigns a good or perfect topic to each paper in most cases when using the provided framework and taxonomy of topics.

¹ Provided to the authors by the teaching team.

Figure 3. A pie-of-pipe chart showing the results of our indexing evaluation. The pie chart on the left shows whether the papers were determined to have a topic that fits. The pie chart on the right shows whether the papers which were determined to have an appropriate topic on the left chart were also found to have their best fit topic assigned to them.

During the indexing, we determined what the best fit topic for a paper would be if the current topic did not apply as the best fit. Notably, this was done only when the paper was still deemed to fit the field of Earth and Planetary Science. Otherwise, the paper was marked as being indexed in the wrong field, and no better fit topic was assigned.

Although OpenAlex only provides one primary topic per paper (Thelwall & Jiang, 2025), any user who opens the API provided on the information page is able to access additional topics deemed relevant to each paper by the LLM as pictured below.

Figure 4. A screenshot of the API provided by OpenAlex for a specific paper. The screenshot shows the topics deemed relevant to the LLM numbered in order of priority (determined using the score,) 0 being highest priority (and the topic under which the paper is indexed) and the priority decreasing as the number increases.

Using the evaluators' judgment of a paper's better fit and the LLMs' alternative topics provided by the API, the authors determined whether the LLM's indexing of works in OpenAlex yielded a more appropriate alternative topic. We found that in most cases where the topic was not the best fit (58% of the time), the paper did not make sense within the field of Earth and Planetary Sciences in the first place. Additionally, when the paper did fit in the field of Earth and Planetary Science, the best fit topic we determined was not a provided alternative topic in the API in the majority of cases (87.5% of the time.)

Are OpenAlex alternative topics the best fit?

Figure 5. A pie-of-pie chart showing whether the alternative topics provided within the API lined up with the best fit that we determined. The pie chart on the left shows whether we determined a paper to fit in the field of Earth and Planetary Science. The pie chart on the right shows whether the papers which were re-assigned topics by the authors were assigned the same alternative topic by the OpenAlex indexing system.

Overall, we have determined that most papers indexed by OpenAlex were indexed under the best fit possible provided the established indexing system (123/200 papers, see Fig. 1.) Notably, when the topic assigned to a paper was not the best fit, the automatic indexing of papers generally missed the mark entirely (45 papers of 77 were in the wrong field, while 28 of the remaining 32 did not provide the best fit even as an alternative topic in the API.) Further study of these papers, which did not fit the best-fit criteria, is recommended to improve the automatic indexing of papers going forward. More research into the papers that were erroneously indexed under the field of Earth and Planetary Sciences is especially recommended to correct future indexing and improve the findability of papers under the OpenAlex system.

4. Conclusion

The evaluation of OpenAlex's classification and indexing of Earth and Planetary Sciences reveals a system with notable strengths but also areas requiring refinement. OpenAlex's open access model and machine-readable architecture make it highly accessible to researchers, librarians, and data scientists. Established fields such as Geology, Oceanography, and Atmospheric Science are generally well represented, providing a reliable foundation for bibliometric analysis and scholarly retrieval. However, weaknesses are evident in the uneven distribution of topics, occasional inconsistencies in hierarchical relations, and gaps in emerging areas such as Planetary Habitability, Exoplanet Geology, and Advanced Climate Modelling. These shortcomings limit OpenAlex's ability to fully capture the dynamic and interdisciplinary nature of Earth and Planetary Sciences. The trade-offs between breadth and depth are particularly noticeable: broad coverage can come at the expense of detailed granularity, while meticulous indexing risks fragmentation and reduced discoverability.

This evaluation also highlights methodological limitations. Quantitative analyses in Excel provide useful descriptive statistics but cannot capture the full complexity of semantic relations. Accessing the OpenAlex API offers greater flexibility but requires technical expertise. Qualitative assessments depend heavily on domain knowledge, which may vary among evaluators, underscoring the importance of delegating the evaluation of specific topics to experts in those areas.

To address these challenges, OpenAlex should expand its taxonomy to include emerging topics, refine hierarchies to eliminate inconsistencies, and calibrate indexing granularity to balance recall and precision. Such improvements would enhance retrieval, support more accurate bibliometric analyses, and strengthen OpenAlex's role as a reliable KOS. Ultimately, refining the classification and indexing of Earth and Planetary Sciences will improve OpenAlex's utility and contribute to the broader goal of advancing scholarly communication and knowledge discovery across disciplines.

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